

1KSA Terms of Use

Data Access, Use and Publication by the Sample Contributor

The 1KSA project stores all sequencing data (pod5, FASTQ, and fasta files) on DIRISA, a secure data storage platform of The National Integrated Cyber Infrastructure System (NICIS). You, the sample contributor, will receive a copy of your data and are free to use and re-analyse it (non-exclusively) for three years.

If you wish to publish research using the raw data, you must upload the data to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), using “1KSA project- *Species Name*” as the sample title and “1KSA- Nanopore sequencing and draft genome assembly of *Species Name*” as the project description.

Your publication must cite this data, make use of the Acknowledgement statement (see below) and must be checked by the 1KSA Data Access Committee (1KSA-DAC) prior to publication.

1KSA encourages publications in Open Access Journals and publication of a preprint in bioRxiv. If the sample contributor does not publish within the three year period, the 1KSA project will upload the fastq and fasta files to ENA after three years using the project tags described above. Pod5 files are currently not accepted by ENA but will be included once ENA adds this functionality. The sample contributor may motivate to the 1KSA-DAC for a public embargo period on ENA to be applied in particular circumstances. The 1KSA-DAC framework on the 1KSA Zenodo community will provide further information.

Data Access, Use and Publication by other scientists

The 1KSA-DAC committee also reviews requests for access to the pod5, fastq and fasta files. This includes collaborators of the sample contributor. Within the first three years of sequencing, the sample contributor will be consulted. Data will be made available under the conditions of a detailed Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) between the 1KSA project and the scientist requesting access to the data.

Open Science

We encourage you to follow Open Science and Open Data principles by sharing your research results openly. This includes popular science articles, GitHub repositories, digits etc.

Acknowledgements

Please acknowledge the 1KSA project, DIPLOMICS, CHPC, DIRISA, and the DSTI in all presentations and publications using your data.

The following acknowledgement statement can be used:

“The authors acknowledge draft genome sequencing provided by the 1KSA project (www.1KSA.org.za) with support provided by DIPLOMICS through the South African Department of Science, Technology and Innovation’s South African Research Infrastructure Roadmap (SARIR). The National Integrated Cyber Infrastructure System (NICIS) is acknowledged for 1KSA data management and curation through the Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa (DIRISA) and for 1KSA draft genome analysis using the Centre High Performance Computer (CHPC)”

Reporting and Publicity

DIPLOMICS will request information about your research progress, such as publications, funding obtained, and trained students, to which you must comply. DIPLOMICS will also publicise the sequencing of your samples in reports and media channels.

Intellectual Property and Benefit Sharing

You (the sample contributor) and/or your institution own any intellectual property (IP) developed from the draft genome assembly, such as patents or inventions. However, we recognise that South Africa’s biodiversity is a national resource, and the 1KSA project was funded by the Department of Science, Technology and Innovation (DSTI) through the SARIR programme and DIPLOMICS. To share the benefits of this research, a portion of any royalties earned from commercially valuable IP will be contributed to the 1KSA Education Program. This program, established by DIPLOMICS, aims to promote biodiversity genomics education in South Africa. You and/or your institution are responsible for tracking and reporting any commercially valuable IP to the 1KSA-DAC and contributing to the education program as needed. This also applies to scientists who have downloaded the 1KSA data sets from the INSDC or have obtained the data through the 1KSA-DAC and used these data sets to generate IP resulting in the sale of a product or payment of commercial royalties.

Version History

Version	Date Modified	Significant changes	Author	Next review date*
1.0	2 September 2024	Document Finalised, to reflect Terms of Use on www.1ksa.org.za	Shane Murray	-
2.0	8 May 2024	Document reviewed, DAC added, Terms of Use updated on www.1ksa.org.za	Shane Murray	30 April 2026

**This document will be reviewed and revised every 12 months*